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Impacts Of Insecurity On Homeownership And Residents' Migration In Kano Metropolitan: A Case For Community Policing

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ABSTRACT

The concept of community policing is relatively a new philosophy that gained its relevance from the compelling need to reposition policing in Nigeria. The concept is trusted on the understanding that the responsibility for neighborhood policing and the mandate should be borne by both the police and the community so that the community is actively involved in fighting crimes within the neighborhood. This is a major shift in paradigm from the traditional reactive mode where policing is only by a regimented authority usually prompted to service by calls from distressed citizens to a proactive model where citizens act as the eyes of the police and being effective partners in fighting crimes. The pace at which this concept is being embraced in the country has been slow mainly due to the quasi-military orientation of the police. The study is therefore an enquiry into how the stake of citizens in property ownership can be harnessed to deepen their participation in community policing for effective implementation. A mixed method research approach was adopted with empirical data on the vacancy ratio of three kinds of residential properties from 2010 to 2015, then from 2016 to 2020. Data were also collected on the emigration profile of 'home owners' and the 'non-home owners' The data were presented in tables and charts to observe changes in residential property occupancy ratio in the period of crisis (2010 to 2020) as well as the migration profile of homeowners as contrasted to non- home owners. The study concludes that the innate need of home owners for the safety and stability of their neighbourhood can be capitalised upon by law enforcement organisations to promote the tenets of community policing. It recommends increased access to resources by citizens such as to facilitate their attainment of home-owner's status

Keywords; community policing, Home ownership, Migration

INTRODUCTION

Since the wake of the Boko Haram (BH) insurgence, there has been an increased spate of insecurity in Northern Nigeria occasioned by kidnappings, banditry, terrorism and other crimes. The Global Terrorism Index, in 2015, classified Boko Haram as a world class terrorist group which has been perpetrating its offensives in Northern Nigeria since 2009 (Global Terrorism Index, 2015). Living condition in the region was characterised with intense fear and anxiety - the fear of a citizen that sometime, somewhere, an explosion of bomb could occur likely in a mosque or church, a supermarket or a car park and the victim could be anyone, either himself or someone he knows (Felbab-Brown et al., 2020; Gaidam, 2015) The situation has ravaged the regions' civic and economic wellbeing. People at all levels of socio-economic strata were not safe. Life in the region was characterized with fear and anxiety. Sequence of attacks by the

group has culminated in a breach of security and marred economic activities in major cities (Bardwell & Iqbal, 2020)

Kano being the main commercial hub of the North was not spared in the spate of these crisis. There were series of attacks on the city, which left residents in perpetual state of fear and anxiety. In January 2012, a series of bomb attacks took place in Kano. 162 people were reported to have been killed. State Security agencies and other public establishment were attacked. The SSS, (State Security Service) Headquarters, four Police Stations, Passport office and Immigration centres were attacked. The heinous terrorist organization *Jama'atu ahlus Sunnah Lidda'wati wal jihad* (a.k.a *Boko Haram*) was principally responsible. Kano, according to media reports suffered attacks that led to colossal loss of lives and properties which left residents in perpetual state of fear and anxiety. Stakeholders including government and non-governmental organizations took a review of the situation and came to a consensus that Policing, through the community, is necessary to create the wide-scoped effective vigilance to supplement the existing security architecture in the country.

The effect of the crisis on socio-economic life is believed to have not only impaired the robust economy of Kano but induced citizens to flee the city for safety leading to the flight of many residents from their homes while those that did not move had their businesses crippled. Studies on the crisis have hitherto, focused on its impact in the macro-economy realm but none, specifically, addresses such micro-economic implications of the crisis as its influence on the behaviour of real estate owners in a metropolis like Kano.

This paper takes a view of the pattern of resident's migration to study the response of home owners to the crisis in contrast to those who owns no property assets and the implications of these responses on community policing measures through the following specific objectives;

1. To examine the trend in the vacancy ratio of residential properties within the metropolis.
2. To examine the emigration profile of home-owners and non-home owners of emigrants
3. To examine the impacts of insecurity on home ownership and residents' migration
4. To offer recommendations on how to reduce the impacts of insecurity on home ownership

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Related Studies

The prospect and challenges on community policing in Nigeria concludes that no significant success has been recorded since the concept of community policing was introduced in Nigeria (Gbenemene & Adishi, 2017). This is apparent in the way the public perceives the police as corrupt and untrustworthy. This mistrust is hinged on the believe that men of the police at times abet criminals and have, on several occasion, been caught as connivers in criminal acts. This pattern sharply contradicts their expected role in community policing scheme which emphasizes partnership with community in ensuring that law and order prevail over crime.

A study on community policing and security situation in Abraka kingdom, Delta State of Nigeria, reveals that the current security challenge in the region requires a collaboration between the community and the police against the causes of insecurity (Gbenemene & Adishi, 2017). The study concludes that the police alone is unable to secure the lives and properties of people of the communities in Delta State and that a synergy between the police and the community can actually bring about better security in the State. The study recommends the enactment of law by the state parliament for the establishment of an organ to train the vigilante groups for effective community policing in Delta and other States in the Federation.

Oikhala (2021) studied the imperative of Community Policing in Nigeria by examining the impact of community policing on the statutory functions of the Nigerian police and reported that the reactive policing model adopted in the country appeared ineffective in curbing the rampant insecurity bedevilling it. It posits that while community policing is helpful to curbing insecurity .in Nigeria, its efficacy is reduced by array of the operational agenda of the Nigerian police. The study recommends that the statutory functions of stemming insecurity in the country would remain a mirage without the active participation of the community.

Conceptualizing Security and Insecurity

Security is a state of peace, calmness, tranquillity and wellbeing of the individual due to the absence of violence, danger, anxiety or any form of psychological trauma. It connotes a state of safety, certainty and protection by which there is the absence of hazard (Okolie & Ezirim, 2020) Security can be seen from two dimensions. First, it is the state of safety from actual danger or the threat of danger, danger itself meaning vulnerability to harm or injury. The second dimension of security, connotes a state of protection from risk or anxiety. Anxiety is however, a subjective negative emotion associated with perceived mishaps. Security therefore entails the entrenchment of peace via freedom from both forms of worries (Niyi, 2020)

Issues of security has been a foremost concern of government all over the world, it is topical in any development discourse. Attempts were made in recent times to broaden the concept of security by broadening its scope beyond a state centred concept to the security of the individual who constitutes the element of national security, also beyond military to non-military matters (Jacob, Jacob, & Ahmad, 2024) Various perspectives in the conceptualization of security in the literature are of two major school of thought; the neo-realist theory school which portrays security as the basic duty of the state, and the plural or postmodernist school, which portrays security as the duty of non-state officials. (Jacob, Jacob, & Ahmad, 2024). The advocate of the second view emphasised that the economic security of individual citizens is more important and thus deserve more attention from government that the security of the nation as the very root causes of security are economic issues. Other scholars in their idea of what constitute security lay emphasis on the absence of threats, the presence of stability, peace and national cohesion. (Odey & Nanji, 2024). There is therefore a consensus among contemporary scholars that security is germane for peace and sustainable development of a national peace (Akpa, Okoro, Ogoko, & Stephen, 2024)

Conceptually, insecurity is the antithesis of security and by this token, connotes the concepts that are the opposite of security such as hazard, danger, fear, lack of protection, uncertainty, lack of safety. Insecurity denotes a state of anxiety or fear due to the absence of protection it connotes being vulnerable to threats and the occurrence of danger, it is therefore a violation of peace and security (Okoli, 2022).

One of the primary purpose of the existence of state is the provision of security for its citizens (Gorka, 2023). The Nigerian Constitution (1999) underscored this fact by stating that “The security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government”. Regrettably, the failure of the Nigerian government in this responsibility is manifested in the abysmal level of insecurity in the country. This is fuelled by terrorists’ attacks in major cities in the North with disastrous consequences on the region’s and national economy.

Home Ownership and Propensity for Migration

A Home refers to any building that is used as, or is appropriate for use as, a dwelling or abode for specific individual or group such as a fam (Rispin & Phil, 2021). The drive for home ownership is so fundamental that it is considered not just a mere desire, but an imperative to man as it underpins his quest for shelter - one of the three basic needs of man. Once acquired, home ownership creates in people, greater sense of inclusion, greater civic attachment and of course, greater stake in the well-being of the community This sense of attachment lowers residents’ propensity for migration and deepen their motivation towards protecting the community in general. The huge capital involved in property investment also makes it the most important investment decision which most individuals or a household would ever undertake and would therefore not be ready to wish away very easily (The Appraisal Jour nal, 2022). Having invested their life savings and depend on income derivable from these properties, they become crucial stakeholders whose participation in community policing is needed. An evidence of this is the fact that in many areas citizens make deliberate efforts at seeking relevant agencies and political bodies to see to the protection and maintenance of their neighbourhood.

A riot is a temporary disturbance with few long-run implications with the consequence that residents and businesses would relocate to more secured regions with higher quality of public infrastructures and

amenities (Ujene, 2018). Bardwell and Iqbal (2020), and Jarvis et al. (2011) observes that insecurity and fear of crisis usually leads to flight of people from the city to the suburbs thereby turning an urban core to an area of concentrated poverty and racial/ethnic enclave in its wake.

While it is true that crisis situation connotes a general risk to investments, the Real Estate Investment sub-sector is exposed to greater risk compared to other assets due to two major peculiarities – its immobility and illiquidity attributes. The fact that real estate is tied to a particular location makes it more vulnerable to risk of the local economy in which it is situated. As perceptions regarding one owns community deteriorate, urban residents often choose to move from an impacted community in search of safer neighbourhood.

Community Policing and its Importance in Nigeria

The Nigerian Police Force by its statutory responsibility is required to engage in numerous activities bordering on the fight against crime and its control. It is important to consider a coordinated intelligence gathering and visual policing that would involve foot and vehicular beat patrols; some tactical point strategies like nipping point, observation point, hot-spot or vulnerable point, pin-down point, stop and search point etc. (Nebo & Ndukwe, 2022). Hitherto, policing in Nigeria has been of a method that was essentially traditional and prompted by the occurrence of incidence, totally exclusive of citizens' participation. This model, has not in any way helped the police to live up to its statutory role (Shimawua, 2021). This is evidenced in the fact that there is no day without a record of crime in form of burglary, robbery, stealing, rape, murder, bombing, etc. (Umar & Formnya, 2024) also acknowledge the inadequacy of the traditional policing model and maintained that the Nigerian public from inception, sees modern policing as a regiment that does not enjoy public confidence as was extremely demonstrated in the “#End SARS” protests (Okolie & Ezirim, 2020). Therefore, the need to introduce the participating hands of the community into conventional policing.

Thus, policing through the community otherwise known as community policing is the involvement and participation of the citizens in securing their community by playing active roles in collaboration with the formal security outfits such as the police, customs, immigration military etc. to give effects to processes and interventions that ensure the maintenance of law and order in the society (Nebo & Ndukwe, 2022).

It is essentially a bilateral strategy which involves synergy between community members and the traditional police force for the purpose of minimising crime and making the community safer. It is also called community oriented policing. As a proactive strategy to law enforcement that places a major emphasis on fostering relationships between police officers and the communities they serve, community policing has gained popularity in recent years (Jacob, Jacob, & Ahmad, 2024)

Crime and insecurity issues are well related to socio-economic controls and politics, thus, much can be achieved by solving the problem of insecurity and crime by putting them in a politico-economic perspective. Such new approach is expected to engage the police in fostering collaboration with cognate agencies saddled with the duty of providing security to curtail crimes. In Nigeria, poverty level got to the extent that the country was listed as the eight poorest nations in the world (Ikenga, 2023) This probably explains the high rate of crime in Nigeria, which is believed to be the direct consequence of poverty and the economic hardship plaguing Nigerians- situation capable of tempting people into crime. Arase (2016) supports the problem-solving model by advocating that police officers should embrace it by developing synergy with the community they serve. The main trust on which contemporary thoughts in community policing is premised is citizens' involvement (Rispin & Phil, 2021). It is therefore apt that any strategy in this direction should leverage on the interest of community members for success. On the other hand, the desire for homeownership has long been ingrained in the fabric of society, symbolizing stability, investment in one's future, and a sense of belonging.

This study identifies the drive for home ownership as one of such interest that could be leveraged upon. Being so fundamental, this drive is considered not just a mere desire, but an imperative that underpins his quest for shelter - one of the three basic needs of man. Once acquired, home ownership creates in people, greater sense of inclusion, greater civic attachment and of course, greater stake in the well-being of the

community. An evidence of this is the fact that in many areas citizens make deliberate efforts at seeking relevant agencies and political bodies to see to the protection and maintenance of their neighbourhood. This study is therefore an attempt to examine the potency of this drive in deepening the sense of inclusivity and how it can be harnessed for the purpose of effective community policing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopts the non-experimental survey design to study two variables; Home ownership identified as the independent variable i.e. the change inducing variable; Residents propensity to migrate, identified as the dependent variable i.e. the outcome variable. The later concept was broken down into specific variables that allows it to be quantified. The choice of non-experimental survey design is informed by the nature of the study being about the relationship between two phenomena – ‘home ownership’ on one side and ‘residents’ mobility’ (i.e. disposition to relocate) on the other hand. The study was conducted in a socio economic setting where it is not practicable to subject the variables to the strict control of a lab setting, hence the choice of this design. The research adopts a population study to obtain data from 75 Estate Surveyors who are all practitioners in Kano metropolitan.

The instruments employed for data collections in this work are questionnaire and Interview guides. The questionnaires, structured and consisted of close ended questions was administered to the field staff of the Estate Surveying and valuation firms. Open ended questions were avoided to minimize responses that would not address the subject matter of the study. The interview guides with unstructured and open ended questions were specifically addressed to the heads of firm.

The questionnaires were constructed to solicit response on the dependent and independent variables in the study. The questions were specific to data relating to the study area- Kano being one of the cities that suffered substantially from Boko Haram (BH) related attacks and which caused many residents to flee the city.

For reliability, the instruments were constructed under the keen supervision of a senior scholar and have been subjected to the views and critiques of experts in the field. The choice of estate surveyors as respondents is to ensure that data collected for the empirical analysis come from reliable sources. The estate surveyors and valuers, besides knowing what other citizens know about the spate of BH crisis, are key participants in the property market.

Table 3.1: Questionnaires Administration

<i>Questionnaire</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>No. Retrieved</i>	72	96
<i>Not retrieved</i>	03	4
<i>Total Issued</i>	75	100

Source: Author’s Construct (2025).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.2: Showing Vacancy Ratio of Residential Properties

		2010-20015		2016-2020	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
<i>Block of tenement property</i>					
	0-25%	41	56.94	62	86.11
	26-50%	25	34.72	8	11.11
	51-75%	6	8.33	1	1.39
	76-100%	0	0.00	1	1.39
	<i>Total</i>	72	100.00	72	100.00
<i>Block of flats</i>					
<i>2-BR</i>					
	0-25%	37	51.39	52	72.22
	26-50%	30	41.67	16	22.22
	51-75%	4	5.56	3	4.17
	76-100%	1	1.39	1	1.39
	<i>Total</i>		100.00	72	100.00
<i>3-BR</i>					
	0-25%	40	55.56	56	77.78
	26-50%	29	40.28	11	15.28
	51-70%	2	2.78	5	6.94
	76-100%	1	1.39	0	0.00
	<i>Total</i>	72	100	72	100.00

Source: Author’s Field Data (2025)

The vacancy ratio of residential properties were as shown in table 4.1 above. An average of 52.8 % of the respondents across the sectors shows that vacancy ratio was within 0 -25% in the period 2010 to 2015 while a sectoral average of 77.8 % indicated that vacancy ratio ranged between 0- 25% in 2016-2020. 36% indicated that the average vacancy ratio of residential properties rose up to the second quartile (26-50%) in the period of 2010- 2015 while only 13.3% of the responded indicated that it reached this level in period of 2016 – 2020. This has shown that the year 2010 to 2015 witnessed the emigration of many people from the metropolitan with the consequence that many residential properties were vacated. The table thus reveals that a higher proportion of respondents indicated that vacancy ratios were higher in. (2010-2015) the peak of the insurgency than as it was between 2015 to 2020 when the crisis became less intense in Kano metropolitan.

Figure 4.1: Showing the emigration profile of Home owners and Non-Home owners from 2010-2020
Source: Author’s Construct (2023)

Figure 4.1 shows the emigration profile of home owners and non-home owners indicating that the home owners demonstrate greater resistance against the urge to migrate than do the non-home owners. This illustrates the psychological effect of home ownership explained above.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that the desire to become a homeowner can be a strong motivator for enhancing community policing programs and creating safer, more cohesive communities. Thus, a symbiotic relationship between homeownership and community policing can be fostered through inclusive strategies that support homeownership access, foster trust between residents and the police, and attend to the needs of the entire community. Thus, law enforcement organizations can capitalize on the innate need for security and stability that homeownership embodies by coordinating homeownership objectives with community policing tenets. This will result in improved community engagement, long-term crime prevention, and an overall improvement in quality of life. Therefore, the study recommends as follows;

Aligning homeownership with community policing;

Homeownership is often associated with stable communities. From the trends in migration as shown in the study, it is imperative for law enforcement agents to collaborate with homeowners. By leveraging the intrinsic motivations driving individuals towards homeownership, law enforcement agencies can establish stronger connections with community members and foster a sense of shared responsibility for neighbourhood safety as homeowners often have a vested interest in maintaining the safety and security of their communities, which will lead to lower crime rates and a greater sense of collective responsibility among residents.

Initiatives such as community watch programs, neighbourhood patrols, and collaborative problem-solving workshops should be more effectively implemented in communities with higher rates of homeownership, as residents are likely to be more invested in the well-being of their neighbourhood.

Need for promoting homeownership;

When residents own homes in a neighborhood, they often have a stronger sense of ownership and investment in the well-being of the community. To harness the drive for homeownership as a tool for community policing, it is essential to ensure that individuals have access to resources and support for achieving homeownership. This may involve providing financial literacy education, facilitating affordable housing options, and offering incentives for first-time homebuyers. By addressing barriers to homeownership, such as limited access to credit or unstable employment, communities should empower residents to take pride in property ownership and actively contribute to community policing efforts.

Building Trust and Collaboration;

Central to the success of integrating homeownership and community policing is the cultivation of trust and collaboration between law enforcement agencies and residents. Police officers must engage proactively with community members, listening to their concerns, involving them in decision-making processes, and demonstrating a commitment to serving the community's best interests. Through regular communication and partnership-building activities, mutual trust should be established, paving the way for effective crime prevention strategies and improved overall community well-being.

Enhancing Policing by the Engagement of Homeowners in the Community:

The government should promote community-oriented policing by active collaboration with Homeowners and integrating local residents into security strategies thereby fostering trust between law enforcement agencies (police) and the people.

Addressing Root Causes of Insecurity;

Socio-economic issues such as unemployment, poverty, and lack of education should be addressed to reduce crime rates and enhance national security.

Incentivizing Real Estate Investment in Safe Zones

Policies should be implemented to encourage real estate development in areas with robust security measures, ensuring long-term investment sustainability.

FURTHER RESEARCH

While this study inquired into the possibility of property owners keying into community policing for effective implementation of community involvement in policing, it will also be ideal to further examine the relationship between the size of property holdings and crime prevention in terms of community policing. Likewise, it may be worthwhile to venture into researching concerning the relationship of non-resident landlords often referred to as 'absentee landlords' and community policing as they have a junk of investment properties within Kano metropolitan. Even though they are often less likely to have an interest in the wellbeing of the surrounding neighborhood and community, however, it is important to subject this to further investigation.

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